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Compressive Failure of Hybrid CFRP-CFRP Laminated Composites

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Background: Sailing yacht masts

- Long and slender (90m+)
- Thick laminates: 4-150mm
- Primarily compressively loaded and stiffness critical
 - Leads to use of high (HM) and ultra-high (UHM) modulus fibres
- Local areas of high-strength requirements
 - As the stiffness of carbon fibres increases, their strength generally decreases
- Combining different stiffness carbon fibres offers opportunity to tailor strength and stiffness

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Background: Hybrid laminates

- Most of the previous research on hybrid laminates has been focussed on combinations of different fibre types such as carbon and glass
- Often this has been to improve laminate toughness (pseudo-ductility) while still achieving good stiffness
- Hybrids can be:
 - Intrayarn: Combined at the fibre/yarn level
 - Intralayer: Fibres incorporated together in one layer
 - Interlayer: Different fibre layers/plies laid up together in one laminate
- Not much work has been done on CF-CF Hybrid laminates

Objective and approach

- Investigate how hybridisation of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminates affects strength and stiffness under compression
- Physical testing undertaken of compressively loaded hybrid laminates with varying proportions of High Modulus and Ultra-High Modulus carbon fibres
- Specimens with 3mm holes were also tested to determine the effect of hybridisation in the presence of a stress concentration
- Failure events within both specimen types were monitored through Acoustic Emission testing and high-speed imaging
- Finite element and analytical models were used to investigate internal ply stresses and strains at failure

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Laminates

- Prepreg materials: Toray UHM (M46J) and HM (M40J) carbon-fibres, Hankuk RS4545 epoxy at 32% by weight
- Base laminate was a 67% 0°/22% +/-45°/11% 90° lay-up, ~2.5mm thick
- Four levels of hybridisation; 33% on-axis UHM, 50% on-axis UHM, 60% on-axis UHM and 100% on-axis UHM, also non-hybrid entirely HM and UHM
- Most UHM plies were blocked together, with an additional 50% on-axis UHM laminate with the UHM plies distributed
- The laminates were laid-up by hand, debulked every 3rd ply for a minimum of 15 minutes, then autoclave cured at a pressure of 4 bar + vacuum.

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Testing Methodology

- Based on ASTM standard D6641 (Combined Loading Compression)
- Specimens 140mm long, 13mm wide, 13mm gauge length
- Some specimens had aluminium tabs
- Specimens with a 3mm hole were also tested
- Vallens AMS3 Acoustic Emission system and high-speed photography used to characterise failure modes

Modelling Methodology

- Purpose was assessment of intralamina and interlaminar stresses within the test specimens
- 3D ply-by-ply finite element model of a tabbed CLC specimen model
- Refined model in gauge length for interlaminar stresses
- Model without end-tabs also developed for the notched specimen case

Results: Laminate Modulus

Results: Failure Modes

- Three distinct modes of failure
 - Full brooming
 - Tab-end damage and splitting
 - Tab-end damage and brooming
- No consistent patterns of the modes of failure over the specimen types
- High stiffness laminates had less extensive regions of damage
- 33% and UHM consistently delaminated at the 0/90 interface before final failure

(a) Brooming

(b) Splitting

(c) Tab End damage

Results: Failure Stress

Results: Failure Strain

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Results: Acoustic Emission

- The 50% (D) and 66% cases that displayed a positive hybrid effect had concentrations of events at the beginning and end of the loading events
- Loads between 30% and 90% of the maximum load did not result in much failure activity
- Could indicate late initiation of failure or delay in the propagation of failure.

Results: Effect of holes

- Dominated by the stress concentration caused by the hole
- Addition of even a small percentage of UHM resulted in a significant decrease in failure load
- Very little acoustic emission pattern variation over the laminate tests
- Suggests that failure initiates and propagates in a very similar way in every specimen

Results: Predicted Ply Stresses (S11)

- HM 50% (D) and 66% laminates fail when the HM plies reach their expected failure stress or strain
- All of the other laminates fail when the UHM plies reach their failure stress or strain.

	HM	33	50	50D	66	100	UHM
Max HM	977	784	776	1000	926		
Max UHM		860	860	1108	1025	856	854

Conclusions

- The carbon fibre hybrid laminates generally followed a linearly proportional rule of mixtures for axial compressive modulus
- Both the 66% and 50% (D) specimens showed a 'positive hybrid effect' for strength, while the 33%, 50% and 100% specimens failed at the expected failure load of the lowest-strength (UHM) ply
- There were no consistent patterns of the modes of failure, other than high stiffness laminates showing less extensive regions of damage and two laminates (33% and UHM) consistently delaminated at the 0/90 interface before final failure
- In specimens with a hole, the stress concentration was shown to dominate failure, with all laminates failing at the expected strength of the lowest strength ply
- The stress analysis showed that the HM, 50% (D) and 66% laminates failed when the HM plies reach their expected failure stress or strain. All of the other laminates failed when the UHM plies reach their failure stress or strain

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